

IMPACT OF COVID PANDEMIC ON THE LIVELIHOOD OF INFORMAL MIGRANT WORKERS IN ANDHRA PRADESH AND TELANGANA

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Abstract: Majority of the migrants working in informal sectors such as construction, brick kits, stone crushing, quarries, agriculture (sugar cane), hotels, varied employees in shopping malls, and other private establishments, domestic servants etc; in destination. The announced sudden lockdown to arrest the spread of Corona virus in different parts of the country. As a result all the informal establishments shut down and the migrant workers lost jobs and also faced various problems in reaching their native places such as decrease in income, transportation, hospitals, education of children, payment of house rents, household consumables etc.; The government launched relief measures to bail out these people from the lockdown crisis like financial help, household groups, medical assistance etc. Main objective: To assess the impact of covid pandemic on the livelihood of migrant workers in informal sectors working in Andhra Pradesh and Telangana. Both primary and secondary data was used in the study. Interview schedule was used in the collection of primary data from the selected sample migrant workers in the study area. Multistage random sampling method used in the selection of respondents. The total sample of the study comes to 400 respondents, representing two districts and two states. Frequency percentages and chi-square test in study.

Key Words: Covid-19, livelihood; informal sector; migrant workers; health; education; welfare schemes.

Introduction:

Migration from one area to another in search of improved livelihoods is a key feature of human history. These moves might be of short to long distance as well as of short to long duration. It is evident from the available literature that there is a widespread occurrence of temporary and seasonal migration for employment in developing countries. Temporary migration is also one of the most significant livelihood strategies, adopted by the poor section in rural India, predominantly in the form of seasonal mobility of labour.

According to 2011 census the

migrants in India is 45.6 crore, constituting 38% to the total population of the Country. Of the total migrants 99% are internal and one percent are immigrants.

Migration of workers from one state to another state is a continuous process, and dynamic in nature. As per Census 2011 data, the total number of inter-State migrant workers in the country are 4,14,22,917. Out of the total workers 3,50,16,700 are males and the remaining 64,06,217 are females. Madhya Pradesh has highest no. of migrants followed by Andhra Pradesh, Tamilnadu, Gujarat, Karnataka, Uttar Pradesh,

West Bengal, Chhattisgarh, Jharkhand, Kerala.

Internal migration can be classified on the basis of origin and destination. One kind of classification is: i) rural-rural, ii) rural-urban, iii) urban-rural and iv) urban-urban. As per the 2011 census, there were 21 crore rural-rural migrants which constitute 54% of internal migration (the Census did not classify 5.3 crore people as originating from either rural or urban areas). Rural-urban and urban-urban movement accounted for around 8 crore migrants each. There were around 3 crore urban-rural migrants (7% of classifiable internal migration). Another way to classify migration is: (i) intra-state, and (ii) inter-state.

In the year 2011, intra-state movement accounted for almost 88% of all internal migration (39.6 crore persons). There is variation across states regarding inter-state migration flows. 2011 Census data shows that there were 5.4 crore inter-state migrants.

Reasons for migration:

Following are the major reasons for migration.

- Extreme poverty and destitution.
- Opportunity for better wage and livelihood.
- Industrial development induced displacement.
- Natural disasters and armed conflicts and
- Human trafficking.

A migration that occurs as a result of any or all of these factors is known as distress migration.

Push factors:

- Poverty and starvation.
- Unemployment.
- Low agricultural productivity.
- Crop failure.

- Landlessness.
- Lack of irrigation sources/ facilities.
- Low level of education and medical care.
- Lack of institutional credit facilities.

Pull Factors:

- Better standard of living.
- Scope of employability.
- Better Gender equality.
- Prospect for better life.
- Better amenities/ civic facilities.
- Wage differentials.
- Bright City life.
- Children's future.

Push and pull migration factors donot function in isolation of one another. Labourers migrant when there is lack of suitable options for employment in their native villages / source places with an expectation of availability of work and better income at the destination. However, the push factors play a vital role in distressed seasonal migration.

Social Security Schemes for Migrant workers:

Recognising the difficulties faced by migrant workers due to sudden lockdown across the Country, the Government of India introduced schemes to mitigate the migrant workers in India and necessities for migrant workers like food, cloth and shelter provided. Besides, the Government distributed relief materials in cash and kind to the migrant workers to overcome the financial distress and also socio-psychological problems.

Migrant workers in Andhra Pradesh and Telangana:

The migrant workers coming from different states to Andhra Pradesh Telangana are found mainly in the following activities and districts -

- Odisha: Brick kilns in Vizianagaram, Visakhapatnam, Nellore, Chittoor in

Andhra Pradesh and Rangareddy, Medak, Warangal in Telangana. Stone crushers in Krishna, Prakasam District in Andhra Pradesh and Ranga Reddy and Vikarabad in Telangana.

- Kerala : Sea foods and Fish processing units in Nellore, Andhra Pradesh.
- Uttar Pradesh : Security Guards in Hyderabad and painters and construction works in Ranga Reddy in Telangana.
- Bihar : Construction labour in Andhra Pradesh and Telangana.
- West Bengal: Bar and Restaurant and also security in Visakhapatnam in Andhra Pradesh and Hyderabad and Ranga Reddy in Telangana.
- Karnataka: Hotels in Hyderabad and Ranga Reddy (Telangana).
- Rajasthan : Marble and granite designers in Hyderabad and Ranga Reddy (Telangana) and Visakhapatnam in A.P.

Inter-district migration in Andhra Pradesh and Telangana:

- Mahaboob Nagar (old), Telangan.: Building and other construction activities in Telangana.
- Guntur and Prakasam (old), Andhra Pradesh: Building and other construction activities in Telangana.

Migration to other Countries from Andhra Pradesh and Telangana:

- **Karim Nagar & Warangal in Telangana and Visakhapatnam in A.P:** Construction works in Dubai, Oman, Kathar etc. drivers and cleaners in Dubai, Oman, Kathar etc.

Covid-19 Migrant workers:

As the infection started spreading across the globe, the Government of India, as part of their initial response, put into place a one-day lockdown called the

‘Janta curfew’ on 22 March 2020.

The Government of India took a sudden decision to impose a complete lockdown of all economic activities across the Country on 24th March 2020, which was a shocking 4-h notice. Lockdown was implemented because novel coronavirus has already punched in Europe and positive cases continue to rise while the health infrastructural system of India was not well equipped for a battle with unknown nature of such deadly virus. Moreover, it was not sure that a vaccine will be found soon. Thus, lockdown was the best strategy for the Government for effective preparedness to defend such crisis.

Phase wise details of lockdown:

The lockdown had been triggered in India in four phases, when the livelihoods of these poor women were in peril and, in six unlock phases they were just confused and disoriented. These consecutive lockdowns and unlock phases were just adding the humiliation to the wound of the people engaged mainly in informal sectors throughout India for out migration.

Lockdown phases :

- 25.03.2020–04.04.2020
- 15.04.2020–03.05.2020
- 04.05.2020–17.05.2020
- 18.05.2020–31.05.2020

Migrants who have left their workplaces and returned to their states of origin also face challenges. The states of origin are quarantining migrant returnees. Initially this was done as self-regulated home quarantine but more recently at Government or community-based quarantine centres close to their homes. These centres have limited capacity, and there is not enough information available for migrant workers about these centres and how they are operated. In some cases,

returnees are met by fear from their community members which may fuel stigmatization and discrimination.

Government Initiatives for the Welfare of Migrant Workers:

The State Governments were asked to use the state disaster response funds for relief measures for migrant workers. The Central and State Governments set up shelter camps for migrant workers and pilgrims along the highways, including tented accommodation, to ensure that they stay in the camps till the lockdown orders are in place. The shelters were organized in a holistic way to provide migrant workers with food and nutrition, clothing, primary health care, and preventive care, maintaining social distancing, counseling, and psychological support. Both the Central and State Governments took initiatives to create awareness, through different sources including NGOs' services, on the facilities being offered to migrant workers.

PM SVANidhi Scheme:

The Scheme was launched to facilitate collateral free working capital loan upto Rs.10,000/- of one-year tenure, to approximately, 50 lakh street vendors, to resume their businesses.

State migrant cell:

Migrant worker's Cell is being created to prepare a database of migrant workers in states with mapping.

eShram portal:

It is a national database created to register the unorganized workers in the country, including the migrant workers.

National policy on migrant worker:

NITI Aayog has been mandated to prepare a draft national policy on migrant workers to reimagine labour-capital relations while integrating the migrant workers within the formal

workforce.

Other Programmes:

During Covid – 19 pandemic period, the Union Government has taken several special measures for generating work opportunities, such as; benefits of Rs.4378.44 crores have been credited in the EPF accounts of 54.67 lakh beneficiaries through 1.3 lakh establishments under Atmanirbhar Bharat Rozgar Yojana (ABRY) till 26.03.2022, benefits of Rs.2567 crores to retain 38.91 lakh low wage employees under Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Yojana (PMGKY), Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Rojgar Abhiyan (PMGKRA) generating 50.78 crore mandays with Rs.39,293 crores, working capital loan to street vendors under PMSVA Nidhi Scheme and special training programme under Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana in the selected districts having high concentration of returnee migrant workers.

COVID-19 has had a catastrophic effect everywhere, infecting and killing millions while disrupting livelihoods and economies worldwide. But it has affected migrant households disproportionately, as a vast majority of them are employed in the informal sector such as construction, services, tourism and hospitality, with little to no job security and social safety nets. They have been the first ones to lose jobs in large numbers, and even among those who have not, a majority live and work in precarious conditions, which put them at a higher risk of catching the highly contagious virus. For migrants who come from low-income households, this has also disrupted a vital income stream that helped their households stay afloat even during local shocks. Therefore, it is pertinent to understand the impact the pandemic has had on the income flows of

migrant households, in turn affecting their financial choices as well as their overall financial well-being.

Relevance of the Study:

As per the review of literature, most of the studies were conducted to study the impact of Covid-19 on the socio-economic conditions of the migrant workers in different states of the country. No direct study was conducted to study the impact of Covid-19 on the livelihood of migrant workers working in informal sectors in the States of Andhra Pradesh and Telangana. Hence the present study.

Main objective of the study:

To assess the impact of Covid-19 on the livelihood of informal workers in Andhra Pradesh and Telangana.

Research Methodology and Approach:

Universe of the study: Andhra Pradesh and Telangana.

Sample of the Study:

Primarily the Project Director visited the offices of the Department of Labour and Employment, Government of Andhra Pradesh and Telangana States for secondary data on migrant workers in informal sectors. As per the outcome of the interactions and discussions with the concern officers of both sample states the Project Director came to conclusion that there is no official data on migrant workers.

Multistage stratified random sampling method was adopted in the selection of sample respondents for the study. Finally in the first stage, from each of the selected state, one district i.e. (erstwhile) Warangal District in Telangana and (erstwhile) Chittoor District in Andhra Pradesh selected for the study because of these two Districts have highest number of migrant workers working in various informal sector. In the second stage, from each of the selected

district in Andhra Pradesh one Municipal Corporation i.e. Tirupati, one Municipality i.e. Madanapalli and two rural mandals i.e. Tirupati Rural and Puttur Rural were selected for the study. With regard to the State of Telangana, Warangal Municipal Corporation, Janagama Municipality and Parakala and Mahaboobabad rural mandals were selected for the study. In the third stage from each of the selected Municipal Corporations, Municipalities and mandals, 50 migrant workers those who engaged in different informal works during the Covid-19 pandemic was identified and selected as respondents for the present study.

This includes inter-state migrants, intra-state migrants and inter district. Thus the total sample of the study consists of two districts, two Municipal Corporations, two Municipalities and four mandals representing 400 respondents.

Sources of data: Primary and secondary sources of data.

Method of Data collection:

Primary data:

Structured interview schedule was used in the study. The schedule consists of two sections. First section deals with the socio-economic profile of the sample respondents and their families (at source place / native villages). The second section deals with the profile of the respondents, details about migration, working and living conditions, impact Covid on the respondent families etc.

Secondary Data: Secondary Data also used in the study.

Data processing and analysis: special package for social sciences (SPSS) 26.0 version.

Statistical Techniques: frequency, percentages and chi-square test.

Conclusions:

- Out of the total respondents, backward castes are predominant (33%) followed by scheduled castes (32%), scheduled tribes (24%) and other castes (10%). Seen Andhra Pradesh sample, 33% are from scheduled castes, 31% from backward castes, 27% belongs to scheduled tribes and 9% from other caste whereas in Telangana BC's are more in the total sample followed by SC's, ST's and OC's.
- A Large percentage of the total population of the sample families (65%) are found in the age group of 10-20 to 40-50 years, 24% are in between 50-60 and 60 years and above and 11% are found in below 10 years. Seen state wise data, more or less similar findings are noticed in both the sample states in all the categories of age groups.
- Majority of the population of the sample families are males (52.12%), of which 53.56% are from Telangana sample and 50.72% from Andhra Pradesh. 47.88% are females, more no.of them are found in Andhra Pradesh than Telangana.
- 69% of the total population are married, seen state wise data more or less similar results are observed in this category. 17% are unmarried, of them 18% are from Andhra Pradesh and 16% from Telangana.
- Out of the total population 38% are illiterates, seen state wise data more no.of illiterates are found in Telangana sample than Andhra Pradesh. Of the total literates population, 34% had studied up to primary level of education followed by secondary level of education (24%) and intermediate level of education (4%). 42% of the total population had primary education in Andhra Pradesh followed by secondary education. In Telangana 28% had studied up to secondary level of education followed by primary education (26%).
- Agriculture is the primary occupation (70%) of the heads of the total sample families at source place followed by agriculture labour (72%), wage work in MGNREGA, rearing of livestock, seasonal / small business etc. state wise data also shows that similar type of occupations were carried out by the respondents.
- Out of the total families 38% have no land, of them 44% are from Telangana and 32% from Andhra Pradesh. The remaining families (62%) have land and it ranges from below one acre to 4-5. Majority of the land owing families are belongs to marginal and small category of farmers.
- Half of the total sample families have no livestock and the remaining families have livestock such as cows, buffaloes, sheeps, goats and pigs. Most of the sample villages at source place have no veterinary services.
- 23% of the total families are found in the annual income range below Rs.40,000 to Rs.40,000-50,000, nearly 70% of the families are found in between Rs.50,000 – 60,000 to Rs.90,000-1.00 lakh and only 4.75% of the families are found in Rs.1.00 lakh and above.
- 56% of the total sample families are found in the approximate annual expenditure range between Rs.70,000-80,000 to Rs.1.00 lakh and above, close to 26% of the total families are found in the range of Rs.50,000-60,000 to 60,000-70,000 and the remaining families i.e. 18%

- are in below Rs.40,000 to Rs.40,000 – 50,000.
- 90% of the total sample families are found in the savings range of Rs.15,000
 - 20,000 to 30,000-35,000 and the rest are in between Rs.35,000-40,000 to Rs.45,000-50,000.
 - Out of the total indebted sample families, 37% are found in the debt range in below Rs.40,000 to Rs.40,000-50,000, 61.50% are found in the range of Rs.60,000-70,000 to Rs.90,000-1.00 Lakh and above. The remaining families 7.25% are in the debt group between Rs.80,000-90,000 to Rs.1.00 lakh and above.
 - Employers (30%) followed by money lenders (30%), labour contractor (18%) plays an important role in advancing credit to the indebted sample families.
 - The indebted families raising credit for the purpose of agriculture works (35%), followed by household consumption (21%), education (8%), health (5%), house construction and repairs (20%), purchase of small assets (10%) etc.
 - 4, 5, 3 and 7 member families are more in the total sample families (86%) in the study. seen state wise data, 4 and 5 member families are more in both the states sample. Average size of the total sample families comes to 4.42 persons. With regard to Andhra Pradesh sample the average family is 4.50 members and 4.35 members in Telangana sample families.
 - Majority of the sample families are nuclear type of families. Only 8% are joint families. State wise data shows that more no.of nuclear families are found in Andhra Pradesh than Telangana.
 - 55% of the total respondents are living in own houses and the remaining are in rented houses. State wise data shows that in the case of own houses more no.of families are noticed in Andhra Pradesh sample than Telangana.
 - Half of the total sample families are living in semi-pucca houses (50%) followed by pucca houses (40%) and Katchcha houses (10%). Seen state wise data semi-pucca and pucca houses are more in number in both the sample states.
 - 62% of the total houses have two rooms followed by one room houses (24%) and three rooms (13.50%). Two and one room houses are more in both the sample states.
 - Public taps and hand pumps acted as major source of drinking water to the total sample households and similar findings are noticed in both the sample states.
 - All the sample houses have electricity connection.
 - Large percentage of the total sample houses have toilet facilities (68%). State wise data shows that more no.of houses have toilets in Andhra Pradesh sample than Telangana.
 - Majority of the total sample houses have bathrooms and same results are noticed in both the sample states.
 - Nearly 62% of the total sample families using LPG as medium of cooking. State wise data shows that more no.of families are noticed in Andhra Pradesh than Telangana.
 - Nearly 70% of the total respondents are from inter-state and the remaining are from intra-state. State wise data shows that more no.of inter-state migrant workers are found in Andhra Pradesh

- sample than Telangana.
- Majority of the total respondents are from rural areas and state wise data shows that similar findings noticed in both the sample state in this aspect.
- More no.of respondents are males in the total sample as well as in both the sample states.
- 83% of the total respondents are in between the age group of 31-40 to 41-50 years and the remaining 17% are in the age group of 51-60 to 61 and above.
- 40% of the total respondents are illiterates, of them 44% are from Telangana sample and 37% from Andhra Pradesh. Of the total sample 32% have studied up to primary level of education followed by secondary education (22.50%) and only 5% had intermediate level of education. Seen state wise data more no.of respondents had primary education in Andhra Pradesh. In Telangana more nof.of respondents had secondary level of education.
- Large percentage of the total sample are married (72%) followed by unmarried (13.50%), widow / widowed (7.75%) and divorce / divorcee (6.5%). State wise data shows that more no.of married are found in Telangana.
- Overwhelming majority of the total respondents are taking short term migration and only 10% of the them are found in long term migration.
- Majority of the total respondents are stay in destination between 7-9 months, in this case more no.of respondents are noticed in Andhra Pradesh than Telangana.
- Of the total respondents 76% migrating once in a year followed by 13% twice in a year and 10% thrice in a year for the last five years.
- Following are the major reasons for migration by the respondents. Low wages (89%) followed by indebtedness (62%), rainfed agriculture (58%), no land (53%), small and marginal land holdings (52%) and crop failure (26%), additional income (35%) and high level of aspirations (76%) were the major reasons
- 53% of the total respondents working in between 20-25 working days, 31% in between 25-30 days and 15% in between 15-20. Seen state wise data majority of the workers are working between 20-25 to 25-30 days per month in Andhra Pradesh 86%, similar findings with small percentage of difference is noticed in Telangana (83%) in this aspect.
- Nearly 47% of the total respondents are working between 9-10 hours per day, in this case more no.of workers are noticed in Andhra Pradesh than Telangana. 45% of them worked between 6-8 hours, of which 47% are from Telangana sample and 43% from Andhra Pradesh.
- Nearly 40% of the total respondents are found in the monthly income of below Rs.25,000, 32% are in between Rs.25,000-30,000, 19.75% are in Rs. 35,000- 40,000 and 8.50% are in between Rs.45,000-55,000. State wise data shows that in Telangana sample (37%) more no.of respondents are found in the income range of Rs.25,000-30,000 when compared to Andhra Pradesh it is 27%.
- Nearly 44% of the total respondents are getting their payment on weekly basis, 32% monthly basis and the remaining 23% daily basis. In both the sample states more no.of workers are getting their wages weekly.
- Majority of the total respondents (81%) are residing in rented houses

- at destination and the remaining 19% living in free housing provided by employers.
- Of the total respondents nearly 40% are living in pucca houses, 39% in semi pucca and 21% in Katchcha houses. State wise data shows that more no.of workers in Telangana are living in pucca houses when compared to Andhra Pradesh where as in Andhra Pradesh majority are living in semi pucca houses.
 - Out of the total sample houses close to 53% have two rooms, 39% have one room and only 8% have three room houses.
 - 76% of the sample houses have bathroom facility, in this aspect more no.of families are found in Andhra Pradesh than Telangana.
 - Majority of the total sample houses have toilet facilities (81%), of which 83% are from Andhra Pradesh and 79% from Telangana.
 - In total and also in both the sample states more percentage of the total sample families depends on public tap water for drinking purpose.
 - All the sample families in both the states have electricity connection to their houses.
 - 79% of the total sample families using LPG as cooking devise, of which 83% are from Andhra Pradesh and 75% from Telangana.
 - Of the total respondents 30% are found in construction followed by brick making (28%), 21% working as salaried employees in different private establishments, housemaid works (6%) and 6% are in transport / auto mobile sector. Seen state wise data more no.of them are in brick making followed by construction and salaried employees in different establishments in Andhra Pradesh.
- In Telangana sample more no.of them are found in construction followed by brick making and salaried employees in private sectors.
- 37.50% of the total migrant workers accompanied by two family member followed by 34.25% one members, 11.50% three members, and in 12.50% of the families no member came along with the respondents.
 - In 48.85% of the total sample families, one member employed in their work followed by 39.69% two members, 11.45% three members.
 - 75% of the total respondents opined that the sudden announcement of lockdown by the Government is bad practice. Seen state wise data more no.of workers are found in Andhra Pradesh than Telangana.
 - Nearly 20% of the respondents not stranded at destination due to sudden announcement of lockdown. 25% stranded around 15 days followed by 23% around 10 days and 21% around 20 days. The remaining 10% stranded between 25-30 days and above. Seen state wise data more or less similar findings are noticed with minor percentage of difference in both the sample states.
 - 58.50% travelled in the Government arranged vehicles to reach their native places, seen state wise data, more no.of respondents are found in Andhra Pradesh sample (63%). 41.50% travelled in private trucks arranged by themselves, such percentage being higher in Telangana sample (46%).
 - 92% lost their jobs, such percentage being higher in Andhra Pradesh sample (97%) than Telangana (87%). 92.25% of faced huge financial crisis, seen state wise data more no.of respondents are found in

- Telangana sample (93.50%) than Andhra Pradesh (91%). 21.25% reported that they did not had nutritious food during lockdown period. 27.50% of the total respondents said that they did not had 3 meals in a day, such percentage being higher in Telangana sample (29%) than Andhra Pradesh (26%). 20% unable to pay the house rent, such percentage being higher in Telangana sample (21%) than Andhra Pradesh (19%). 19.75% faced difficulties in meeting their basic needs, seen state wise data more no.of respondents are found in Andhra Pradesh sample (20.50%) than Telangana (19%).
- Government extended help to the respondents in the following aspects during lockdown such as free food ration by State Government (25%), Grocery kits (65%), Employer provided food grains and vegetable kit (46%), Food from community kitchen (14%), NGO or philanthropist provided food kits (10%), Free food ration under Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Yojana (36%) and house rent waived off by the owner (30%).
 - 56% of the total families had savings at the time of lockdown, of which 104 families are from Andhra Pradesh and 121 are from Telangana.
 - All the sample families are indebt, the debt amount ranges from below Rs.40,000 to Rs.70,000 and above. Overwhelming majority of the respondents (91%) are in the debt range between below Rs.40,000 to Rs.60,000-70,000.
 - 67% of the total respondents received full salary last month of working i.e. before announcement of lockdown, 28% got half salary and the remaining 4.50% did not received salary.
 - With regard to support extended by the employer during lockdown: Extra payment (4%), assurance for future hike in salary (10%), material (groceries) support (14%), One-month advance salary paid (10%), frequent phone calls and enquiry(12%), assuring work after lockdown (15%) and no support (33%).
 - Expectations from the state support by the respondents: ensuring minimum wages (18%), financial support for one year (31%), job security at workplace (27%), support with ration/groceries (24%).
 - Impact of Covid on the sample families: short term-debts increased (7.75%), food intake restricted (9.25%), food basket not diversified (17%), difficult to pay rent (29%), withered savings (26%), and selling of personal assets (10%). Long term-financial insecurity (27%), debt increased (7%), job insecurity increased (47%), and marital relationship affected (19%).
 - 35% of the total respondents said reduction in household income in between 40-60%, 27% between 10-20%, 21.25% between 20-40%, 16.75% between 60-80% and only 2% felt no reduction in the household income during lockdown.
 - Out of the total respondents, 89% borrowed loans from money lenders and 11% did not raised loans. Those respondents who raised credit are divided into below Rs.10,000 to 25,000 and above. 69% of the total respondents are found in the debt range between Rs.10,000-15,000 to Rs.25,000 and above 20% are found in below Rs.10,000.
 - Out of the total respondents, 36%

managing the household expenses with reduced income, 16% relatives are supporting, 26% existing saving is used, 19% managing with borrowed money and 3.25% not affected much.

- Following are the experience of the respondents faced during lockdown such as severe sleep pattern (45%), some times feel anxious (29%) and rarely anxious (14%). Out of the total respondents who faced severe sleep pattern (No.182) discontinued the health treatment due to unaffordability (30%), lack of transportation (33%), and no outpatient services in Government Hospitals (35%).
- Out of the total respondents 216 have Jan dhan accounts, of which 118 are from Andhra Pradesh and 98 from Telangana.
- Out of the total Jan dhan account holders (No.216), 72 got financial help, of which 37 are from Andhra Pradesh sample and 35 from Telangana.
- Impact on overall spending by the sample families during Covid lockdown: no change (7.25%), spending increased highly (20.75%), spending increased moderate (21.25%), spending increased slightly (35.75%) and decrease in spending (15%).
- Increase in overall spending by the respondent families during lockdown: health care cost (13%), childrens education(10%), debt – interest related payments (27%), hygiene related costs (17%) and increase in prices of essential commodities (32%).

Recommendations:

- Overwhelming majority of the respondents are belongs to Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes and Backward Castes, in order to reduce

the rate of migration the origin state Government should take measures to strengthen the Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes and Backward Castes welfare schemes for the development of these people.

- 35% of the sample families are engaged in wage work in MGNREGA at source place. Increase the budget allocation for MGNREGA to reduce the migration.
- 40% of the total respondents are illiterates and the remaining are poorly educated, policy must create labour – intensive as well as capital intensive jobs in informal establishments, so that both skilled and unskilled workers can be benefited. There is the need to develop a training module for illiterate and less educated workers in rural and Urban areas so that the informal sector can absorb them easily in better productive and remunerative activities.
- Close to 40% of the total families are landless, the Government should provide agriculture land to the landless families.
- Nearly about half of the total sample families have no livestock, in our study area livestock also secondary sources of income to the people. The Government should provide loans including subsidy to the people to purchase the livestock.
- In most of the sample villages (at source places) have no veterinary health care centres. The Government should take measures to establish such centres.
- The role of banks is minimal in extending advances to the sample families. The Government should strengthen the banking system particularly in rural and drought

- prone areas including SC and ST should be streamline to avoid migration.
- Most of the sample families raised credit for agriculture purpose. Government should provide input subsidy to the marginal and small farmers.
 - A large percentage of the sample families are residing in semi-pucca and Katchcha houses, sanction houses under Prime Minister Awas Yojana (PMAJ).
 - Most of the migrant workers were engaged in unskilled and semi skilled type of works at destination. Provide skill development training in different trades to the respondent families who return at source places.
 - Strengthen the sources of irrigation such as tanks, supply channels, check dams, ponds etc. for cultivation at source places to reduce the dependency of farmers on rain-fed agriculture.
 - Improve the living conditions of the respondents at destination such as accommodation including basic amenities.
 - The banks should come forward to lend the advances to the distressed return migrant workers (after lockdown) to start income generating activities or self employment at native places.
 - The Government should implement short term measures for social protection of the migrant workers should include distribution of temporary compensations such as food tokens/ vouchers, PDS ration and cash transfers for a long term.
 - Provision should be made for free health care facility / schemes to the migrant workers in both private and Government hospitals at source and destination during pandemics.
 - Government should be developed mechanisms to ensure temporary relief or provision of extended time to pay rent and utility bills. This could be monitored/ liason by NGO's, Local body or the law enforcing agencies.
 - In order to ensure rights inclusive of labour rights to migrant workers, their emotional, psychological, social, economic and political well being needs immediate attention. In a futuristic perspective, the informal sector which employer mostly migrant workers requires wellfarist, rights based as well as and inter sectionality approach with long term goals. The efforts should be taken by through the involvement of multiple stakeholders- central to state agencies, labour welfare activist, workers association, NGO's, researchers etc.
 - Efforts should be made to undertake reforms in the existence labour laws by strengthening institutional machanisms for holding employees liable for violation of migration labour rights.
 - The standards for work conditions and remuneration must be implemented properly.
 - Self employed are fully insecure and face unique livelihood risks, given their importance to society, there is a need to think about the welfare of these workers.